

PRODUCTION OF THE JOSHI EFFECT IN OXYGEN UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE. PART II. INFLUENCE OF INTENSITY AND FREQUENCY OF THE INCIDENT RADIATIONS

BY S. R. MOHANTY AND G. S. KAMATH

The Joshi effect Δi in oxygen has been studied at different exciting potentials V of 50 cycles frequency as a function of the light intensity I , and with different wave bands in the visible. At constant V , increase of Δi with I is first rapid; saturation sets in at large I . This has been ascribed, on Joshi's theory, to the development of an opposing electro-static field in the immediate neighbourhood of the photo-active boundary layer on the excited electrodes. The Joshi-Lakshminarayana equation, viz., $\Delta i = aI^b$ (a and b being constants) holds over a fairly wide range of moderate intensities. At higher V , the initial rise of Δi with I and the corresponding tendency to saturation are comparatively pronounced than at a lower V . The non-linear dependence of Δi on I discriminates the Joshi effect from the classical metal-in-vacuum type photo-electric phenomenon.

At a given V , Δi varies in the order: unfiltered white > blue > green-red. The selective absorption of oxygen in the visible is but feeble. It is maximum in the green-red. The Joshi effect is, however, markedly less in this than in the blue, which supports Joshi's postulate that Δi is not a consequence of selective absorption.

The oxygen, activated under the silent electric discharge, shows an appreciable Joshi effect Δi has been established by the authors in a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 405). The present communication reports results for the dependence of Δi on oxygen at different exciting potentials upon the intensity and the frequency of the incident radiations, in the visible.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general experimental arrangement and the procedure for observing Δi were essentially similar to those described in Part I of this series (Mohanty and Kamath, *loc. cit.*). A Siemens' type glass ozoniser filled with purified oxygen at a pressure of 27 mm. Hg (20°) was excited by transformer discharges of 50 cycles frequency in the primary. The current indicator consisted of a sensitive mirror galvanometer actuated by a Cambridge vacuo-junction. A water cell interposed between the ozoniser and the source of radiations, viz., the incandescent (glass) bulb, served to cut off the less refrangible heat rays.

The intensity of the incident radiations was varied by altering the distance d between the ozoniser and the source, in the range of 10—200 cm. The gas was excited at a constant applied V . Galvanometer deflections were noted in the dark, and under irradiation with the source at different d from the ozoniser. From these, the discharge current in dark i_d , that under irradiation i_l , the net Joshi effect $\Delta i = i_d - i_l$ and the proportionate effect $\% \Delta i = 100 \Delta i / i_d$ were calculated. The relative intensities I were computed to a

first approximation from the inverse square law. The variation of Δi with I was studied at different V in the range of 0.8—1.5 kV (r. m. s.). A typical set of observations is shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Influence of light-intensity on the Joshi effect in oxygen at different exciting potentials.

$pO_2 = 27$ mm (20°). Temp. = 27° . Frequency of A. C. supply ≈ 50 cyc./sec.

Detector = vacuo-junction. Source of irradiation = 200 volt, 200 watt (glass) bulb

d.	Intensity (relative) I .	0.8 kV		0.93 kV		1.07 kV		1.2 kV		1.33 kV	
		Δi .	% Δi .	Δi .	% Δi .	Δi .	% Δi .	Δi .	% Δi .	Δi .	% Δi .
10 cm.	10.0	6.33	44	5.66	39.1	4.59	34.8	3.86	29.5	3.93	29.3
20	250	4.5	31.6	4.34	30	3.19	24.2	2.83	21.6	2.94	21.9
30	111	3.71	25.8			2.56	19.4	2.26	17.3		
40	62.5	2.99	20.8	2.86	19.7	1.92	14.6	1.90	14.5	2.24	16.7
50	40.0	2.90	20.2			1.66	12.6	1.50	11.5	1.94	14.5
60	27.8	2.35	16.3	2.21	15.3	1.31	9.9	1.25	9.6	1.67	12.5
80	15.6	1.82	12.7	1.69	11.7	0.98	7.5	0.87	6.7	1.29	9.6
100	10.0	1.66	11.5	1.41	9.7	0.86	6.5	0.67	5.1	1.17	8.7
120	6.9	1.31	9.1	1.00	6.9	0.58	4.4	0.55	4.2	0.89	6.6
140	5.1	1.13	7.9	0.85	5.9	0.43	3.3	0.49	3.6	0.77	5.7
160	3.9	1.04	7.2	0.71	4.9	0.19	1.3	0.39	3	0.46	3.4
180	3.1	0.83	5.8	0.42	2.9	0.19	0.8	0.27	2.1	0.38	2.8
195	2.6	0.68	4.7	0.31	2.1	0.06	0.5	0.23	1.8	0.32	2.4

The effective frequency of the radiations was varied by the use of long strips of coloured glass. The familiar Wratten or similar filters could not be used on account of the appreciable size of the ozoniser which was necessary to ensure a large enough i so that Δi could be observed with sufficient accuracy. The discharge current i due to different V in the range of 0.5—3 kV was observed (i) in the dark, (ii) under irradiation (7800–3700 Å) from a 200 watt (glass) bulb run at 200 volts; and with (iii) blue (5100–

4080Å), (iv) green (6060-4830Å) and (v) red (7390-6010Å) filters added to (ii). The transmission limits quoted above were observed from the corresponding spectra taken with a Hilger constant deviation spectrograph on a Kodak P/1200 super-panchromatic plate with an one minute exposure. Using the water filter, the relative total intensities observed with a Kipps' 37 thermopile were ; unfiltered white (128), red (65), blue (47) and green (3). In Table II, which contains but one representative set of observations, are shown Δi and $\% \Delta i$ for different V under the above wave bands.

TABLE II

Influence of the light-frequency on the Joshi effect in oxygen at different exciting potentials.

$pO_2 = 27$ mm (20°). Temperature = 29° . Frequency of A. C. supply = 50 cyc./sec.

Detector = vacuo-junction. Source of irradiation = 200 volt, 200 watt (glass) bulb.

V in kilo-volts (r.m.s.)	Filtered Red 7390-6010 Å.		Filtered Green 6060-4830 Å.		Filtered Violet 5100-4080 Å.		Unfiltered White 7800-3700 Å.	
	Δi .	$\% \Delta i$.	Δi .	$\% \Delta i$.	Δi .	$\% \Delta i$.	Δi .	$\% \Delta i$.
0.67	0.37	2.7	0.19	1.4	2.76	19.9	4.00	28.8
0.8	0.50	3.2	0.22	1.4	2.93	19	4.14	26.8
0.93	0.33	2.2	0.16	1.1	2.31	15.4	3.38	22.5
1.07	0.24	1.6	0.07	0.5	1.90	13	2.80	19.1
1.2	0.24	1.7	0.10	0.7	1.76	12.1	2.61	18.0
1.33	0.21	1.5	0.07	0.5	1.35	9.6	2.19	15.5
1.47	0.21	1.5	0.07	0.5	1.31	9.3	2.07	14.7
1.6	0.17	1.2	0.10	0.7	1.25	8.8	1.96	13.8
1.73	0.17	1.2	0.10	0.7	1.27	8.8	2.01	13.9
1.87	0.17	1.2	0.07	0.5	1.17	8.0	1.80	12.4
2	0.18	1.2	0.07	0.5	1.00	0.8	1.60	11
2.13	0.17	1.2	0.10	0.7	1.06	7.2	1.62	11
2.27	0.17	1.1	0.11	0.7	1.03	6.8	1.58	10.5
2.4	0.19	1.2	0.13	0.9	0.81	5.3	1.40	9.2
2.53	0.10	0.6	0.07	0.4	0.75	4.7	1.34	8.5
2.67	0.06	0.4	0.03	0.2	0.74	4.7	1.18	7.5
2.8	0.09	0.6	0.03	0.2	0.60	3.7	1.03	6.4

DISCUSSION

Data in Table I show that, similar to the observations of Joshi and co-workers (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, pp. 70-75; *J. B. H. U.*, 1943, 8, 99; Joshi and Deo, *Nature*, 1943, 151, 561; Deo, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1944, 18, 84; *Curr. Sci.*, 1944, 13, 44) in chlorine, Δi in oxygen at constant V increases with I. Further, the variation of Δi with I is more prominent at small values of I, and slows at larger I when Δi tends to a limiting value, indicative of saturation (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 35; 1944, 13, 278). That the variation of Δi is influenced by the initial value of I is evident from the following: At 0.8 kV, *e. g.*, whilst about a four-fold increase of I from 2.6 to 10.0 in relative units enhances Δi from 0.68 to 1.66, *i. e.*, by 2.44 times, a similar rise of I from 10.0 to 40.0 increases Δi only 1.75 times, 1.66 to 2.90. At still higher light-intensities, the rise in Δi with I is but small. Thus *e. g.*, variation of I from 250 to 1000 increases Δi from 4.54 to 6.33, *i. e.*, by 1.39 times. These findings in oxygen support Joshi's observation (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, 70-75; *J. B. H. U.*, 1943, 8, 99), based on the non-linearity of the Δi -I relationship, that this phenomenon cannot, in the first instance, be identified with a possible negative photoelectric effect.

The rate of increase of Δi with I is influenced appreciably by the exciting potential. At higher V, the initial rise in Δi is comparatively rapid; the corresponding tendency to saturation is also more pronounced. Thus, whilst at 0.8 kV, increase of I from 2.6 to 10.0, 10.0 to 40.0 and 250 to 1000 enhances Δi respectively by 2.44, 1.75 and 1.39 times the corresponding values at the lower I, at 1.33 kV the increase is respectively 3.66, 1.66 and 1.33 times.

Joshi and Lakshminarayana (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1945, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abs. No. 12) correlate Δi and I in the form

$$\Delta i = aI^b$$

where *a* and *b* are constants. This gives

$$\log \Delta i = \log a + b \log I,$$

so that the plot of $\log \Delta i$ against $\log I$ should be a straight line. The actual plots (Fig. 1) reveal that the Joshi-Lakshminarayana equation holds over a fairly wide range of moderate intensities, *e. g.*, over $I = 3.9$ to 111 at 1.2 kV. It is significant that such a simple relationship should operate over about a 28 fold variation of I, despite the approximations involved in the assumption of the inverse square law for the large-size body source employed. At very high and very low intensities, however, the equation fails, and a more comprehensive one will be necessary under these conditions.

A possible explanation of the tendency to saturation of Δi at large I suggests itself from the theory of this Δi phenomenon due to Joshi (*ibid.*, 1946, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abs. No. 26, 1947, Abs. No. 25; *Curr. Sci.*, 1946, 18, 281; 1947, 18, 19).

According to this, the formation on the excited electrodes of an adsorption-like ionic + molecular boundary layer is primary to Δi . Photo-electrons released from this layer are captured by the electro-negative gas particles in the discharge space to form slow moving negative ions which reduce i by a space-charge effect. The accumulation of these negative ions in the immediate neighbourhood of the photo-active layer brings into existence an opposing electro-static field which slows down the primary photo-electron emission, leading not only to the non-linear variation of Δi with respect to I , but a disproportionate inhibition to increase of Δi with I .

As is seen from Table II, Δi at constant V varies in the order : white $>$ blue $>$ red $>$ green. The relative effect $\% \Delta i$ also varies in the same order. Thus *e. g.*, at 0.67 kV, $\% \Delta i$ due to (unfiltered) white light was 28.8. This decreased to 19.9 due to the interposition of the blue filter. Substitution of the blue filter with the green and the red filters reduced markedly the magnitude of Δi ; $\% \Delta i$ was, at the above V , 1.4 and 2.7 respectively. The greater Δi under blue despite its low intensity (47), when compared with red (65), indicates, as has been observed by Joshi and co-workers (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, 70-75; Joshi and Deo, *loc.cit.*; *Curr. Sci.* 1943, 11, 306; *Nature*, 1944, 153, 434; Deo, *Sci. & Culture*, 1943-44, 9, 253; *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1944, 19A, 117) in chlorine, that frequency is the more predominant factor than intensity in the production of this phenomenon. That Δi under green was slightly less than that under red might be due to I_{green} (3) being relatively far too small compared with I_{red} (65). With less disparity between I_{green} and I_{red} ,

it is likely that the *effect* in green might be greater than that in red, *i. e.*, frequency-wise.

Oxygen absorbs in the visible, at 7594 Å (red), 6867 Å (red), between 6360 and 6225 Å (orange), 5810 and 5675 Å (yellow), at 5350 Å (green), between 4795 and 4750 Å (blue) and at 4470 Å (indigo) (Jansen, *Compt. rend.*, 1885, **101**, 11, 649; 1886, **102**, 1352; 1888 **106**, 1118; **107**, 672; Egoroff, *ibid.*, 1885, **101**, 1143; Liveing and Dewar, *Phil. Mag.*, 1888, **26**, 286; Dewar, *Chem. News*, 1893, **67**, 210; Shaver, *Proc. Roy. Soc. Canada*, 1921, **16**, 7). It would appear from this that the extent and the intensity of absorption is greater in the red-green than in the blue, which is just the reverse of the order in respect of Δi now reported. Furthermore, the above absorption is detectable only with (up to 60 metres) long tubes filled with highly compressed (up to 140 atmospheres), or with liquefied gas. As suggested by Joshi (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, 70-75) therefore, it is extremely unlikely that the *effect* Δi is entirely a consequence of selective light absorption.

Grateful thanks of the authors are due to Professor S. S. Joshi for suggesting the problem, and for his kind interest and valuable guidance.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
BENARES HINDU UNIVERSITY.

Received May 10, 1948.